

#14

Evaluation & Impact Assessment **JOURNEY MAPPING**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>After an actor/stakeholder has engaged with a project or part of a project to assess the impact of the project where that actor is concerned. This tool can also be used to vision desired impacts of a project in advance of project implementation.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>One to one or group basis (with a maximum of 6 participants).</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Requires use of any online storyboarding tool. Optionally an artist can be engaged to develop a bespoke storyboard.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>2-4 hours (including preparation).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Internet access & use of (free or fee-based) online storyboarding tool. Optionally engage an artist.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2 and 24.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Understand the experiences of an actor/stakeholder with a project/initiative, identifying impacts of the project/initiative and their subjective evaluations of the project/initiative.
- Develop an easy to interpret storyboard about the actor's/stakeholder's experiences, pinpointing events where the project/initiative had impact/s.
- Assess the extent to which the actor's/stakeholder's experiences match with what the project/initiative envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences.
- Vision aspirational/desired impacts of a project in advance of project implementation, periodically thereafter using the 'journey map' to assess how a project is delivering planned impacts.

Background and Logic

Tools such as Tool #11 (causes and effects) and Tool #5 & Tool #6 (needs and motivations registers) generate hypotheses and collect information about the intended impacts of a project/initiative and what actors/stakeholders want from a project/initiative. These are very important planning tools in making reflexive, evidence-based decisions that are attuned to different actors' & stakeholders' needs & motivations in real-life circumstances. However, as the project/initiative progresses and/or matures to completion what were participants' experiences in practice?

This tool takes a 'storyboarding' approach, which generates a visual, easy to interpret account of an actor's/stakeholder's experiences of a project/initiative. It condenses a lengthy story into a shorter account of key events and experiences. It can portray the key events/activities of a project where impact occurred. Intended impacts can be assessed against the actual impacts experienced by participants, as portrayed in the storyboard. Storyboards can be developed to portray the experiences of a single actor/stakeholder or a group approach can be taken, where a group of actors/stakeholders tell their collective stories. Taking a group approach, each actor/stakeholder would have a different character in the story, similar to the approach taken in Tool#3

This tool is inspired by [Wengraf \(2008\)](#) & [Vanclay \(2012\)](#)

Materials:

- Online storyboarding tool or artist
- List of project/initiative *intended* impacts - customised to the actor/stakeholder featured in the storyboard (where relevant).

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.
- Optionally, show examples of completed storyboards, such as those created by the Plutos Horizon 2020 project [here](#) or an animated version from the SWAB project [here](#).

Step 2: Facilitator Preparation¹

- The facilitator acts in an interviewer role. An open-ended approach is taken, inviting the actor/stakeholder to tell their story. No question list of pre-prepared questions is used. The role of the facilitator is to listen and, if necessary, limit questions only to asking more detail about what the actor/stakeholder has told them.
 - It may be the case that a key planned impact does not arise in the story, and if so, this is likely to indicate that the impact did not occur or lacked significance. In such a way, what is absent from the story can be as important as what is in the story.
 - The facilitator should prepare him/herself, where relevant, with a list of the key events/impacts planned by the project/initiative for the actor/stakeholder so that s/he can be attentive to how these are (or are not) portrayed in the story.
- Considering that the storyboard is about interactive innovation, the facilitator should also be attentive to the various multi-actor scenarios – what were the actor's/stakeholder's experiences of these important scenarios in interactive innovation?
 - The most important prompt questions to elicit story type narrative for populating the storyboard are:
 - » Can you tell me the story of your experiences of (project/initiative), all the experiences and events that are important to you personally.
 - » The facilitator (who is acting in a role similar to that of an interviewer) can ask for more detail on the story, such as:
 - Tell me more about how all that happened?
 - Do you remember anything more about that particular moment/time?
 - The storyboard may also portray aspirational/desired impacts of a project, in advance of its implementation. In such a case, appropriate prompt questions are:
 - » Can you tell me the story of what will happen in this project, and how you'd like it to play out? Start from the beginning...

Multi-Actor toolbox – online, interactive version (with links to practical tools) available [here](#).

¹ This approach is inspired by the Biographic Narrative Interpretive Method (BNIM) [Wengraf \(2008\)](#).

- » The facilitator (who is acting in a role similar to that of an interviewer) can ask for more detail on the story, such as:
 - Tell me more about how that might happen?
 - Can you think of any more detail about how that might happen?

Step 3: Create the Storyboard

- The facilitator works with a single actor/stakeholder OR a group (maximum 6), where each has a different character in the story (their real names and characters)
- The storyboard can be created in-person or online (e.g. conversing on Zoom), with the facilitator screen-sharing an online storyboard creator.
- Open an online storyboard creator (such as www.boords.com or www.storyboardthat.com)
- Remind participant/s that all good stories have a start, middle and end! Begin with the question in Step 2 above and *after each significant juncture/main event*:
 - ask the participant/s to summarise what they have said to insert concise text to a scene of the storyboard.
 - Choose an appropriate image for the scene
- Repeat the above until the storyboard is populated with all the main events, told from the perspective of the participant/s.

Step 4: Use of storyboard to assess/ evaluate the project/initiative

- The storyboard portrays participant/s experiences of the project/initiative, telling the story of all impacts as experienced by the participant/s. It provides evidence of the more immeasurable, experiential and unintended as well as intended impact/s of the project/initiative.
- Processes of interactive innovation, such as the key scenarios of multi-actor work, can be qualitatively described.
- Whether the intended impacts of the project were experienced by the participant/s (and how significant they were) can be assessed.
- Storyboards portraying different actors' experiences of the project/initiative can be used to assess varying impacts of the project/initiative among actor types.

<p>4</p> <p>✂ A marketing consultant, Michelle, is approached by Anita. Michelle asks Anita about her marketing approach. She asks, who is the customer (across the value chain), and how Anita manages to convey the values of her product to the end consumer? Does she have certification regarding sustainability & animal welfare standards? How well is this certification conveyed to the consumer? Michelle values change - she supports and seeks to activate changes in consumer demands...</p> <p>Ploutos Focus Group, WP2 V1</p>	<p>5</p> <p>✂ Anita explains to Michelle problems when it comes to implementing new technology on her farm... For cultural reasons.. and maybe due to lack of knowledge of how to use the technology.. Technology is a way of capturing information for the consumer, and is often important for conveying messages to the consumer. In a context where Anita feels that she's not getting rewarded price-wise - there is technology to better capture the measurement of high welfare standards. This technology is essential in collating information and presenting it to the consumer...</p>	<p>6</p> <p>✂ Patrick, a local innovation broker, would like to see improvement where Anita's situation is concerned. He would like to help through programmes & tools, such as innovation programmes, knowledge transfer & exchange initiatives through, for example, the National Rural Networks & through access to databases of projects that help in this area. He focuses on the importance of bringing people together to identify ways for consumers to access products with high welfare and sustainability attributes.</p> <p>Made with Boords 2</p>

Example from Ploutos (Horizon 2020) storyboard

